

AFFECTIVE FILTERS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS: BASIS FOR PROPOSED ENHANCED HOMEROOM GUIDANCE PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between affective filters and academic performance among junior high school students in the Philippines, aiming to inform the development of an enhanced homeroom guidance program. A survey was administered to 240 students, measuring their levels of affective filters across four domains: biological, environmental, motivational, and social. The study found a significant positive correlation between the level of affective filters and academic performance, with the environmental variable exhibiting the strongest relationship. Significant differences in affective filters were observed based on sex, ethnicity, parental employment and educational attainment, family income, and family structure. These findings suggest that affective filters are a significant factor influencing academic performance and that interventions should address both individual and environmental factors. The study recommends strengthening homeroom guidance programs to create a more supportive learning environment, foster student motivation, and promote positive social interactions. By addressing these factors, educators can create a more conducive learning environment that supports students' emotional well-being and academic achievement.

Keywords: *Affective filters, Academic performance, Homeroom guidance, Learning environment, Student Motivation*

INTRODUCTION

The principle of learning individuality remains a fundamental educational thrust, addressing the diverse learning styles and backgrounds of students. Modern educational paradigms emphasize the learner-centered approach, particularly in the 21st century, necessitating educational institutions to prioritize students' learning conditions (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). It is widely recognized that learners' cognitive and affective characteristics influence their learning styles, which vary based on the teaching strategies employed (Ormrod, 2012).

The distinction between cognitive and non-cognitive domains is pivotal in fostering holistic learner development (Good, 2010, as cited in Stalker, 2021). The Department of Education (DepEd) has established policies to support this inclusive approach, addressing learners' affective status, mental health, and other developmental aspects. DepEd Order No. 72 s. 2009 underscores inclusivity, promoting acceptance of all students regardless of their attributes (Department of Education, 2009).

Understanding learners' intellectual and emotional maturity is crucial for effective teaching, aligning with educational principles that incorporate cognitive, psychomotor, and affective domains (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). DepEd Memorandum No. 74 s. 2021 further highlights the integration of mental and emotional health concerns into educational programs, acknowledging the impact of varied learning modalities on school policies and instructional goals (Department of Education, 2021).

The shift to modular learning has posed challenges, affecting not only cognitive and intellectual development but also learners' emotional and social conditions (Sarmiento, 2021). Emotional instability among students can disrupt their learning momentum, necessitating initiatives to promote mental resilience. The DepEd's mental health and psychosocial support programs aim to address these issues, recognizing the significant influence of emotional status on academic improvement (Sarmiento, 2021).

Krashen's (2008) concept of the affective filter, as cited by Cabacchan (2022), refers to negative emotional and motivational factors that hinder the reception and processing of comprehensible input. High affective filters, characterized by anxiety, self-consciousness, and low self-esteem, create mental blocks that impede skill acquisition. Factors such as attitude, communication apprehension, and negative evaluation further contribute to the affective filter (Krashen, 2008).

Understanding affective filters is essential for educators, as it informs the selection of appropriate teaching methods that reduce learning barriers and enhance student engagement (Cabacchan, 2022). Identifying current affective filters among students can help assess the effectiveness of existing learning modalities.

As a mental health advocate and guidance counselor, the researcher recognizes the importance of addressing both cognitive and affective learning aspects to improve learning outcomes. This study aims to examine the affective filters of junior high school students and their correlation with academic performance, providing a basis for

enhancing homeroom guidance programs. The findings will offer valuable insights for school administrators, teachers, guidance counselors, and parents, supporting the implementation of a curriculum that benefits learners.

Research Questions

Generally, the study sought to determine the affective filters and their relationship to the academic performance of Junior High School students.

Specifically, it aimed to seek answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. sex;
 - b. ethnicity;
 - c. sibling order;
 - d. parents' employment status;
 - e. parents' highest educational attainment;
 - f. average monthly family income; and
 - g. family structure?
2. What is the level of affective filters among the respondents in terms of:
 - a. Affective Biological Variable;
 - b. Affective Environmental Variable;
 - c. Affective Motivational Variable; and
 - d. Affective Social Variable?
3. What is the academic performance of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of affective filters of the respondents when grouped according to their profile variables?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of affective filters and the respondents' academic performance?
6. What intervention can be proposed to enhance the homeroom guidance program of the Junior High School students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational design as it examined the relationship between the level of affective filters and students' academic performance. Creswell (2018) categorically defines this research design as the variables and relationships between and among them. The test of relationship details results including positive, negative, mixed, or no relationship at all but does not establish a causal effect.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the schools of the identified high schools in the North District of the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan, Isabela in the School Year 2022-2023. Identified schools are categorized as national secondary schools and integrated schools.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents' sample size was calculated using Slovin's Formula [$n = N/(1 + Ne^2)$]. They were selected through a simple random sampling. The respondents were a pool of students in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan. Specifically, these students were from the identified secondary schools and integrated schools legally and duly registered in DepEd. The table below shows the list of schools and several students in the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan.

Table 1. Sample Size of the Study

North District	Number of Students	Sample Size (Slovin's Formula)
1. Rang-Ayan National High School	602	104
2. Manaring Integrated School	461	88
3. San Lorenzo Integrated School	331	48
TOTAL	1394	240

Research Instruments

The primary data-gathering instrument used was a structured survey questionnaire comprising two parts. Part I elicits the profile of the respondents in terms of their sex, ethnicity, sibling order, parents' employment status, parents' highest educational attainment, average monthly family income, and family structure. On the other hand, Part II consisting of the items on the affective filter was adopted from Cardona's (2015) study. It is a checklist in a 5-point Likert-type gauge. The checklist is composed of the four affective variables with five (5) items for each variable totaling twenty (20) questions. Items are rated as follows: 5 – Very High; 4 – High; 3 – Moderate; 2 – Low; 1 – Very Low. It was validated in a previous study with an acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.746$).

Lastly, the academic performance was taken from the grades as reflected in the official records of the respondents for the Second quarter and Third quarter of the SY 2022-2023.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the school authorities for the conduct of the study. Also, the consent of respondents was obtained. They were informed on the purposes, methodology, and expectations of the study. They were assured that their confidentiality and identity would be maintained.

The researcher floated the questionnaire face-to-face. To ensure 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaire, the researcher supervised carefully the data collection. Furthermore, the grades of the respondents were taken from the official records that are kept by the respective teachers. In compliance with the Data Privacy Act, the researcher

sought first the approval of the respondents and their parents before the grades were obtained.

Data Gathering Tool

All data were tallied and interpreted using different statistical tools. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Probability for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.

Statistical Tool

The statistical tools utilized in treating data to be gathered include the following:
For the first research question, descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency count, and percentage were used to treat the profile variables.

Descriptive statistics was utilized in identifying the level of affective filters among the respondents in terms of affective biological variable, affective environmental variable, affective motivational variable, and affective social variable.

Table 2. Interpretation of the Level of Affective Filters

4.20 – 5.00	Very High
3.40 – 4.19	High
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate
1.80 – 2.59	Low
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low

Furthermore, the frequency count, percentage, and mean were utilized in analyzing the academic performance of the respondents. The data was interpreted as follows:

Table 3. Interpretation of Students' Academic Performance

90 – 100	Excellent
85 – 89	Very Satisfactory
80 – 84	Satisfactory
75 – 79	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	Did not meet expectations

For research hypothesis 1, it was tested using a T-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) while for research hypothesis 2, the Pearson r shall be employed in determining the significant relationship between the level of affective filters and academic performance of students.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 4. Distribution of the Frequency and Percentage of Respondents' Sex, Ethnicity, and Birth Order

Profile	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	127	59.92
Female	113	40.08
Birth Order		
First-born	78	32.50
Middle-born	79	32.92
Last-born	83	34.58
Ethnicity		
Ibanag	54	22.5
Ilocano	148	61.7
Others	38	15.8
Total	240	100.0

The table presents the profile of respondents in terms of sex, ethnicity, and birth order. Of the 240 respondents, 127 (59.92%) were male and 113 (40.08%) were female. When considering ethnicity, most of the respondents were Ilocano, accounting for 148 (61.7%) individuals. Regarding sibling order, the data shows that the sample was evenly distributed, with 78 (32.5%) being first-born, and 83 (34.58%) last-born. The Ibanag ethnic group constituted 54 (22.5%) respondents, while 148 (61.7%) belonged to other Ilocano ethnicity.

Table 5. Distribution of the Frequency and Percentage of Respondents' Employment Status of Parents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Father's Employment Status		
Government Employee	26	10.83
Private Employee	78	32.5
Self-employed	118	49.17
Unemployed	18	7.50
Mother's Employment Status		
Government Employee	20	8.33
Private Employee	52	21.67
Self-employed	130	54.17
Unemployed	38	15.83
Total	240	100.0

The table presented above presents the employment status of parents. Moving on to the employment status of the parents, it is evident that the respondents had varying family backgrounds. Among fathers, 118 (49.17%) were self-employed, 78 (32.5%) were private employees and 18 (7.5%) were unemployed. Similarly, for mothers, the highest proportion was self-employed, with 130 (54.17%) respondents and 20 (8.33%) were government employees.

Table 6. Distribution of the Frequency and Percentage of Respondents' Highest Educational Attainment of Parents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Highest Educational Attainment (Father)		
Elementary Graduate	112	46.7
Highschool Graduate	104	43.3
College Graduate	20	8.3
Graduate of a Post Baccalaureate Degree	4	1.7
Graduate of a Post Graduate Degree	0	0.0
Highest Educational Attainment (Mother)		
Elementary Graduate	102	42.50
Highschool Graduate	74	30.83
College Graduate	56	23.34
Graduate of a Post Baccalaureate Degree	8	3.33
Graduate of a Post Graduate Degree	0	0.00
Total	240	100.0

The table reflects the frequency and percentage distribution of the educational attainment of respondents' parents. Regarding the educational attainment of the respondents' fathers, a significant portion had only completed elementary education, accounting for 112 (46.7%) individuals. Only a small percentage, 20 (8.3%), were college graduates, and an even smaller proportion had achieved a post-baccalaureate or postgraduate degree. For mothers' educational attainment, a similar pattern emerged. The largest group completed elementary education, with 102 (42.5%) respondents, and 8 (3.33%) who a post-baccalaureate degree.

Table 7. Distribution of the Frequency and Percentage of Respondents' Family Income and Family Structure

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Family Income		
15,001 – above	36	15.00
10,001 – 15,000	42	17.50
5,001 – 10,000	58	24.17
5,000 – below	104	43.33
Family Structure		
Nuclear	178	74.17
Extended	62	25.83
Total	240	100.0

Finally, this table reveals the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents' family income and family structure. Examining the average monthly family income, the data indicates that most respondents fell into the "5,000-below" income bracket, with 104 (43.33%) individuals and 36 (15%) respondents having an income of "15,001 and above."

Finally, looking at the family structure, most respondents came from nuclear families, with 178 (74.17%) belonging to this category. The remaining 62 (25.83%) respondents were from extended families.

In summary, the profile of the respondents reveals a diverse sample in terms of sex, ethnicity, sibling order, parents' employment status, parents' educational attainment, average monthly family income, and family structure. These findings provide insights into the characteristics and backgrounds of the participants involved in the study.

Level of Affective Filters of the Respondents

Table 8. Level of Affective Biological Filters of the Respondents

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Interpretation
Factor 1- Affective Biological Variable			
They are willing to learn the concepts of their subjects.	3.77	1.12	Favorable
They are confident in their own learning styles in studying their subjects.	3.53	1.13	Favorable
Whenever they encounter problems inside or outside the school, they relate their learnings to solve such issues.	3.02	1.39	Moderately Favorable
They see learning as an opportunity to help them in their daily tasks.	3.35	1.22	Moderately Favorable
They are committed in my learning of concepts and facts about all their subjects.	3.24	1.33	Moderately Favorable
They don't feel anxious and insecure about their own learnings on their subjects compared to their classmates.	2.73	1.43	Moderately Favorable
Whenever projects are asked by teachers, they don't overthink about the deadline and anxiety doesn't strike me.	2.91	1.34	Moderately Favorable
Overall Mean	3.22	0.60	Moderately Favorable

In the Affective Biological Variable, the respondents displayed moderately favorable level of affective engagement. They expressed a willingness to learn the concepts in their subjects (mean = 3.77) and confidence in their learning styles (mean = 3.53). They also recognized the relevance of their subjects in solving problems (mean = 3.02) and saw it as an opportunity to assist them in their daily tasks (mean = 3.35). Although there was a slight level of anxiety and insecurity compared to their classmates (mean = 2.73), it did not hinder their commitment to learning (mean = 3.24). Overall, the average for this variable indicates a moderately favorable level of affective engagement (mean = 3.22).

This finding implies that the biological factor is a learning hindrance among respondents. Furthermore, according to England (2017), Affective Biological Variable involves those filters that are personal to the individual, including attitude, behavior, and biological features. Therefore, a moderately favorable affective biological variable posits a manageable personal development among the respondents that could hinder learning activities. Students' biological filters self-reported their general class, test, communication, and social anxiety; perceived course difficulty; intention to stay in the major; and demographic variables, as hindering factors toward learning tendencies of

learners. He also indicated that general class anxiety levels differed for students who intended to learn or not.

However, extreme instances may deviate from this general interpretation of the result wherein personal traits of the individual could affect his learning development. This study builds on and expands this former work by investigating biological factors between both general anxiety and a wider variety of anxiety measures and actual student performance and self-reported intention to persist. This, according to Brigati (2019), stated that student anxiety toward active learning could have on these student outcomes.

Low affective filters encourage receptiveness to learning, while high filters hinder acquisition and engagement, with higher filters causing hindered learning transfer and lower classroom engagement.

Table 9. Level of Affective Environmental Filters of the Respondents

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Interpretation
Factor 2- Affective Environmental Variable			
The school where they study has easy access to equipment, tools, and resources that facilitate better learning.	3.43	1.26	Favorable
The school where they study has a conducive learning atmosphere resulting to a better understanding.	3.40	1.16	Favorable
They feel that their subjects provided them with enough experiences to grow in their specific strand.	3.44	1.16	Favorable
The boarding house/apartment/house where they stayed was peaceful and helped me focus during their learning.	3.39	1.37	Moderately Favorable
There is an atmosphere of freedom in the commission of mistake/sin the classroom which strengthens their self-confidence.	2.96	1.46	Moderate Favorable
The school adheres to policies that motivate better learning process.	3.43	1.22	Favorable
The classroom has a TV screen or Projector screen or online classes where they see what they learn that motivates and concretizes our learning.	3.77	1.39	Favorable

Overall Mean	3.40	0.59	Favorable
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The table above reflects the level of Affective Filters on the Affective Environmental Variable, the respondents perceived their learning environment in their subjects to be favorable in terms of affective engagement. They acknowledged that their school had easy access to resources and facilities (mean = 3.43) and provided a conducive learning atmosphere (mean = 3.40). The experiences in their subjects contributed to their personal growth (mean = 3.44), and the boarding house or living arrangement they had was peaceful and conducive to focus (mean = 3.39). However, there was a slightly lower perception of an atmosphere of freedom for making mistakes in the classroom (mean = 2.96). The presence of visual aids such as TV or projector screens in the classroom was seen as motivating and enhancing their learning (mean = 3.77). On average, the respondents reported a moderately favorable level of affective engagement in their learning environment (mean = 3.40). Hence, the higher the mean, the higher the affective filters, leading to a greater tendency to hinder the transfer of learning which is caused by disoriented or disturbance.

This finding indicates that the respondents' environmental setting affects their learning development. Boyd (2021) explained that the environmental setting of learners is an important factor in their academic success and total learning development. Jeremiah (2018) also concluded that academic performance is a positive outcome when learners are nourished in a healthy and harmonious environment, including their home and school. However, a favorable level of affective environmental filters is an example of the negative side. Learners with this learning condition are disoriented, malfunctioning, and disturbed. In addition, according to Policay (2021), the physical environment needs to be practical as well as interesting and stimulating. Arranging the desks and chairs in such a way as to facilitate small-group work, individual work and whole-class discussions is a challenge. The ideal structure should cater to different learning styles and consider the teacher's desk situation, either making it accessible or creating additional barriers.

Furthermore, Butac (2020) highlights the significant impact of the learning environment during the implementation of alternative education delivery modality on learners' development and affective filters.

Table 10. Level of Affective Motivational Filters of the Respondents

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Interpretation
Factor 3- Affective Motivational Variable			
1. They are eager and motivated to learn in their subjects.	3.52	1.16	Favorable
2. They feel relaxed and confident in learning their subjects.	3.36	1.37	Moderately Favorable

3. They are still motivated to learn concepts in their subjects without moral encouragement.	3.49	1.25	Favorable
4. They are still motivated to learn concepts in subjects without material encouragement.	3.45	1.20	Favorable
5. Their own learning experiences in their subjects help them to learn other subject areas.	3.39	1.06	Moderately Favorable
6. Topics in their subjects make them feel like a real scientist which motivates them to learn even more.	3.45	1.23	Favorable
7. Activities in their subjects make them enjoy learning the concepts even more.	3.30	1.23	Moderately Favorable
Overall Mean	3.42	0.56	Moderately Favorable

Table 4.7 shows the level of Affective Filters in the Affective Motivational Variable, the respondents demonstrated a moderately favorable level of affective engagement. They expressed eagerness and motivation to learn their subjects (mean = 3.52) and felt relaxed and confident in their learning (mean = 3.36). They were self-motivated without relying on external encouragement, both morally (mean = 3.49) and materially (mean = 3.45). They recognized that their learning experiences in their subjects extended to other subject areas (mean = 3.39), and the topics in their subjects motivated them to learn more (mean = 3.45). Although the enjoyment of learning activities in their subjects was slightly lower (mean = 3.30), the average for this variable indicates a moderately high level of affective engagement (mean = 3.42).

Consequently, learners with a moderately favorable level of affective motivational filter lack the necessary motivation, inspiration, confidence, and intrinsic and extrinsic factors such as class goals, habits, and the personal inhibitions of the learners that negatively affect their learning development. Hence, a moderately favorable affective motivational filter may hamper academic success since motivation triggers one's behavior or a drive that comes with a goal or incentive.

Moreover, Cheng (2018) revealed that motivation, as described in the study of educational principles and theories, is a teaching ideal that should focus on the learners themselves. On the other hand, motivations could be greatly hampered by affective filters. Motivational variables are also affective filters that may affect the development of learning of the learners and so as their academic performance in a learning area or course of study. Motivation greatly affects the efficacy of the teacher, rather, it affects the learning development of learners which may hinder or induce their performance. Finally, to fully understand the construct of affective filters, social variables should never be neglected. Mentoring has been identified as a mechanism for supporting instructional improvement and learning development, in the compulsory school and higher education contexts.

Table 10. Level of Affective Social Filters of the Respondents

Factors	Mean	Standard Deviation	Descriptive Interpretation
Factor 4- Affective Social Variable			
1. Their teachers in their subjects help them feel confident and have better learning in the subject.	2.87	1.30	Moderately Favorable
2. Their teachers in subjects provide them with immediate, frequent, and task-related feedback to help them improve their learning and their learning styles in the subjects.	3.35	1.36	Moderately Favorable
3. Their parents support and stimulate their interest in having a better performance in subjects' class.	3.40	1.36	Favorable
4. Their classmates in subjects help them cope with the difficulties that they encounter during the learning process.	2.86	1.30	Moderately Favorable
5. Their classmates, teachers and they have a good relationship inside and outside the subjects	2.92	1.30	Moderately Favorable
6. Their peers initiate learning sessions about their subjects in the group.	2.55	1.27	Least Favorable
7. There is no competition of students within the subjects' classes.	2.63	1.18	Moderately Favorable
Overall Mean	2.94	0.56	Moderately Favorable

Lastly, the table above presents the level of Affective Filters in the Affective Social Variable, the respondents perceived a moderately favorable level of affective engagement. They reported that their subject teachers helped them feel confident and improved their learning (mean = 2.87), and they received immediate, frequent, and task-related feedback from their teachers (mean = 3.35). Their parents also provided support and stimulated their interest in performing better in their subjects (mean = 3.40). While they acknowledged that their classmates helped them cope with learning difficulties (mean = 2.86), there was room for improvement in their relationships with peers (mean = 2.92). The initiation of learning sessions by peers within the group was slightly lower (mean = 2.55), and the absence of competition among students in their classes was also lower (mean = 2.63). Overall, the average for this variable indicates a moderate level of affective engagement (mean = 2.94).

This finding implies that respondents have strong social conditions serving as filters in their academic endeavors. Since Affective Social Environment is anchored in the learners' social environment, which includes their parents, teachers, friends, peers, and other socially relevant and significant individuals to the learners, the COVID-19 pandemic characterized by limited peer and teacher interaction might have contributed to this

scenario. As Umar (2020) claimed, an unfavorable social environment may serve as a piece of baggage for an individual to do well academically.

One of the factors identified by Tehseen & Madi (2015) in their study, Factors Influencing Teachers' Performance and Retention, working conditions have an impact on the student's performance and their retention conditions include facilities defined as the physical workplaces of teachers and the available resources to them. Additionally, research conducted by Jeremiah (2018) stated that physical and social learning environments are contributory factors in learning development among students.

Table 11. Overall Level of Affective Filters of the Respondents

Dimensions of Affective Filters	Mean	Interpretation
Affective Biological Variable	3.22	Moderate
Affective Environmental Variable	3.40	High
Affective Motivational Variable	3.42	High
Affective Social Variable	2.94	Moderate
Overall	3.22	Moderate

Legend:

4.20 – 5.00 *Very High*

3.40 – 4.19 *High*

2.60 – 3.19 *Moderate*

1.80 – 2.59 *Low*

1.00 – 1.79 *Very Low*

Table 11 reveals the level of affective filters among respondents. In general, the respondents have a moderately favorable affective filter with a mean of 3.22. In the study by Cardona (2015), a moderately high level of affective filters nears a high level of affective filters characterized by strong filters that affect the learning and development of respondents in a particular course of study. These filters are negative walls that hinder the transfer of learning and are further manifested by negative responses and low levels of student engagement in classroom activities. Previous researchers discovered that students' learning development was somewhat hindered by a moderately high level of affective filters (Akinwumi et al., 2016).

Specifically, learners with a moderately favorable level of affective filters are sometimes anxious during instruction, especially while doing activities related to other students and teachers, classroom control, lesson effectiveness, and lesson presentation. Furthermore, they are often anxious about participating in classroom discussions, thus limiting their maximum performance. A moderate level of affective filters is a relatively unsound level of affective filters because it tends to alter and modify the course of learning developments and academic success of learners. As compared to a high level of affective filters, a moderate level is tolerable and mitigated by classroom techniques and methods that resolve identified problems. On the other hand, a high level of affective filters connotes a bigger problem as it already broadened a wider problem regarding negative

filters present among learners such as anxiety, mental health issues, and other relevant problems.

Academic Performance of the Respondents

Table 12. Frequency and Percentage of the Academic Performance of the Respondents

Academic Performance Level	Frequency (n=240)	Percent (100%)
Outstanding (90 – 100)	60	25.0
Very Satisfactory (85 – 89)	50	20.8
Satisfactory (80 – 84)	50	20.8
Fairly Satisfactory (75 – 79)	75	31.3
Did Not Meet Expectations (below 75)	5	2.1
Overall Mean of Academic Performance	83.92	Satisfactory

The academic performance of the respondents is measured based on their level of achievement in their studies. Table 12 provides the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents' academic performance levels. Most of the respondents achieved a satisfactory level of academic performance, as indicated by the frequency distribution. Specifically, 60 respondents (25.0%) achieved an outstanding level (90-100), 50 respondents (20.8%) achieved a very satisfactory level (85-89), and another 50 respondents (20.8%) achieved a satisfactory level (80-84). A significant number of respondents, 75 (31.3%), obtained a satisfactory level (75-79). Only a small proportion of respondents, 5 (2.1%), did not meet expectations with a performance below 75.

In summary, the respondents' academic performance can be characterized as satisfactory based on the distribution of performance levels and the mean score. Although there were some variations in individual scores, most respondents achieved a satisfactory level of academic performance.

The result affirms the findings of Policay (2021) on the study of the academic performance of students who perform averagely in their subjects. However, this still falls below the curricular goals of the K–12 curriculum, which focuses on the learners' development based on the identified skills and competencies of the new curriculum. Hence, there is a need to augment instruction through enhanced instructional materials and pedagogical innovations in the learning area.

Further, it should be noted that the average grades obtained through the results of the summative examination were from the first and second quarters of the school year during the implementation of the face-to-face instructional modality as part of DepEd's Learning Continuity Plan. Hence, the respondents' satisfactory academic performance in social studies may be attributed to the learning challenge sand adjustments brought about by the paradigm shift in the education system (Salud, 2022).

Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters Grouped by Profile

Table 13. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by Sex

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Affective Biological Variable	0.94	0.39	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	3.92	0.02*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	1.79	0.17	Accept	Not Significant
	Affective Social Variable	2.58	0.08	Accept	Not Significant

The table presents the results of the analysis investigating the significant difference in the level of affective filters among respondents when grouped according to their profile variables. The research problem aims to determine if there are variations in the affective filters based on different profiles. The F-value and p-value are provided for each comparison to assess the significance of the differences.

Starting with sex, the analysis indicated that there was no significant difference in the level of affective filters based on sex. The F-value of 0.94 and the p-value of 0.39 suggested that the observed differences were not statistically significant. Consequently, it can be concluded that the level of affective filters does not differ significantly between males and females. The level of affective filters specifically Affective Environmental Filters differs significantly between male and female learners.

In contrast, a related study by Akinsola (2014) found that sex is a factor in students' learning anxiety, claiming that female students have more effective filters than males, attributed to their varied biological, behavioral, and emotional orientations. This point was also affirmed in the study of Payne and Furnham (2016), which claimed that sex significantly influences students' levels of negative emotions. In a parallel study by Cubucko and Donmez (2016), it was found that female students had a higher level of negative emotions in all dimensions of student engagement in the school. In addition, they manifested a higher level of affective filters as they experienced greater mental and emotional walls hindering their learning development.

Additionally, Payne and Furnham (2021) discovered that gender is a significant factor that might change the level of the negative emotions of learners in a particular learning area.

Moreover, Cabacchan's 2022 study found that male students generally perform better academically than female students, indicating a strong influence of affective filters and their profile variables on academic performance.

Table 14. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by Ethnicity

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Ethnicity	Affective Biological Variable	1.78	0.17	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	7.16	0.00*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	3.88	0.02*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Social Variable	0.15	0.86	Accept	Significant

As for ethnicity, the analysis revealed that there were significant differences in the level of affective filters based on ethnicity. Specifically, the affective filters of environmental and motivational factors showed significant differences. The F-value of 7.16 and the p-value of 0.00 indicated a significant difference between ethnicity and the affective environmental variable. Similarly, the F-value of 3.88 and the p-value of 0.02 suggested a significant relationship between ethnicity and the affective motivational variable.

However, no significant differences were found for the affective filters of biological and social. Therefore, it can be concluded that the level of affective filters differs significantly based on ethnicity, particularly in the environmental and motivational domains. This particularly means that ethnicity influences environmental and motivational levels of affective filters of learners specifically identifying that they are from the Iloko and Ibanag cultural identities. Their ethnic environment and motivational factors brought upon by cultural integration and differentiation are influential in the recognition of present variables towards learning.

In considering learners' ethnic and cultural background for learning development and academic performance, Apolonio (2017), in a local study of Indigenous education,

claimed that the kind of cultural orientation to which the learner adheres determines the likelihood of success in an educational setting. Contrary to this, Osborne (2016) noted that the level of affective filters of learners is affected only if the variables are stated and no other extraneous variables, such as ethnicity or cultural background, influence the study on effective filters.

In contrast, the study by Miller and Wiese (2018) contradicts the findings regarding the relationship between affective filters and ethnicity. They found no significant differences in affective filters based on ethnicity. However, it is important to consider that findings may vary depending on the specific context and sample population.

Table 15. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by Birth Order

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Birth Order	Affective Biological Variable	0.40	0.75	Accept	Not Significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	0.49	0.68	Accept	Not Significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	0.83	.480	Accept	Not Significant
	Affective Social Variable	0.17	0.92	Accept	Not Significant

Regarding birth order, the analysis revealed no significant difference in the level of affective filters based on birth order. The F-values ranged from 0.17 to 0.83, and the associated p-values were all greater than the significance level. Consequently, it can be concluded that birth order does not have a significant influence on the level of affective filters.

This result is supported by Semana (2017) who notes that the sibling order of learners in a particular school is not a contributory factor to learners' affective filters. Further, Krashen (2018) revealed that the affective biological filter is not influenced by birth order, particularly in the learning development of learners.

Table 16. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by Father's Economic Status

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Father's Economic Status	Affective Biological Variable	2.02	0.09	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	5.47	0.00*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	1.68	0.15	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Social Variable	1.18	0.32	Accept	Not significant

In terms of the father's economic status, the analysis indicated a significant difference in the level of affective filters based on the father's economic status. Specifically, the affective filter of the environment showed a significant difference. The F-value of 5.47 and the p-value of 0.00 indicated a significant relationship between the father's economic status and the affective environmental variable. However, no significant differences were found for the affective filters of biological, motivational, and social variables. Therefore, it can be concluded that the level of affective filters differs significantly based on the father's economic status, particularly in the environmental domain

This scenario is negated by several pieces of literature navigating the factors affecting students' academic performance in class. One of which is identified is the parents' socioeconomic status relative to their employment status. Jeremiah (2018) narrated that one of the enormous considerations for learners' success in school is the economic support emanating from parents. Thus, paternal support has been tagged as essential in a family for many economic reasons. Concerning students' learning development in school, students with more and better support from their parents are more likely to perform their daily tasks and activities in school.

Table 17. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by Mother's Economic Status

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Mother's Economic Status	Affective Biological Variable	0.88	0.47	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	4.52	0.00*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	2.94	0.02*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Social Variable	1.78	0.13	Accept	Not significant

For the variable of the mother's economic status, the analysis revealed a significant difference in the level of affective filters based on the mother's economic status. Specifically, the affective filters of Environmental and Motivational showed significant differences. The F-value of 4.52 and the p-value of 0.00 indicated a significant relationship between the mother's economic status and the affective Environmental Variable. Similarly, the F-value of 2.94 and the p-value of 0.02 suggested a significant difference between the mother's economic status and the affective Motivational Variable.

However, no significant differences were found for the affective filters of Biological and Social. Therefore, it can be concluded that the level of affective filters differs significantly based on the mother's economic status, particularly in the Environmental and Motivational domains.

The economic status of maternal support significantly impacts learners' environmental and motivational development, as studies show that high maternal economic support leads to low affective filters in learners' domains.

In the same study by Jeremiah (2018), the unemployment of respondents' mothers negatively impacts children's learning development, but it doesn't guarantee improved school performance when mothers have ample time to teach.

Chen and Zhou's 2017 study reveals significant differences in affective filters among students based on their socioeconomic status, potentially affecting their learning experiences and academic performance.

Table 18. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by Father's Highest Educational Attainment

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Highest Educational Attainment (Father)	Affective Biological Variable	1.48	0.22	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	1.38	0.25	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	2.73	0.04*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Social Variable	1.10	0.35	Accept	Not significant

Regarding the highest educational attainment of the parents, the analysis indicated a significant difference in the level of affective filters based on the highest educational attainment of both the father and the mother. Specifically, the affective filters of motivation showed significant differences. The F-values ranged from 2.73 to 3.63, and the associated p-values were all below the significance level. However, no significant differences were found for the affective filters of Biological, Environmental, and Social. Therefore, it can be concluded that the level of affective filters differs significantly based on the highest educational attainment of the parents, particularly in the Motivational domain.

The result confirms that paternal education level will not directly affect students' learning conditions and educational outcomes. However, Littkey (2004) as cited by Cardona (2015) revealed that when the family head, who is usually a father, makes efforts to educate the children, there is more likely to be a positive reinforcement of educational goals due to the father's influence in the family. The level of education of fathers could also be determinative of learners' success in classroom processes and activities

This learning condition categorically supports the significant difference between the levels of affective filters of the respondents when grouped according to their fathers' educational attainment. As discussed, paternal education affects the learning development of the offspring. This scenario is also characterized by an educational and learning principle wherein the learners' social and parental support are factors to consider learners' continuous development outside the classroom environment. Supporting this point, Akinsola (2017) has established that the higher the father's level of education, the better educational outcomes are deemed expected and realized by their children.

Table 19. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by their Mother's Highest Educational Attainment

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Highest Educational Attainment (Mother)	Affective Biological Variable	1.07	0.37	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	0.90	0.46	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	0.91	0.45	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Social Variable	1.51	0.20	Accept	Not significant

Table 19 shows a comparison of the respondents' level of affective filters when grouped according to mothers' highest educational attainment. It is shown by the data that there were no significant differences established in the respondents' level of affective filter when grouped by biological variable, environmental variable, motivational variable, and social variable. Thus, it is implied that the respondents have the same level of affective filters across the variables.

Previous studies revealed that paternal education level significantly affects their children's learning development and educational success (Tan, 2017). Besides, Cheng (2018), in her study on parenting and scaffolding, also found the same assertions that mothers who are primarily guidance providers and scaffolding masters are hugely affecting their children's total learning development starting even from the early stages of childhood development. Filial support has been recognized as one of the best informal education methods. In the study by Policay (2021), during the implementation of the alternative modalities in education, it was noted that Filipino mothers provide learning and feedback support to their children who are undertaking such modalities. On the contrary, this was one of the causes of a student's low and diminished academic performance in the present study. Hence, the higher the mother's educational attainment, the more scaffolding techniques are provided to their children. The parents' educational attainment contributes to their children's learning development and complete educational experience.

Table 20. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by Family Income

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Family Income	Affective Biological Variable	1.91	0.11	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	2.24	0.06	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	2.00	0.09	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Social Variable	3.43	0.01*	Reject	Significant

In terms of family income, the analysis revealed a significant difference in the level of affective filters based on family income. Specifically, the affective filter of society showed a significant difference. The F-value of 3.43 and the p-value of 0.01 indicated a significant difference between family income and the affective Social Variable. However, no significant differences were found for the affective filters of Biological, Environmental, and Motivational. This means that family income cannot be considered as a factor in considering affective filters. The income of the family does not have any influence or effect on the levels of affective filters in the biological, environmental, and motivational aspects. Therefore, it can be concluded that the level of affective filters differs significantly based on family income in the social domain.

This finding indicates that the financial status of the family of learners, as attributed to their monthly net income, significantly contributes to affective social filters. Tehseen & Madi (2015) noted that conditions in the place and budgeting capacity of their families impact the learners' performance and their retention conditions, which include facilities and school support materials present in their homes and available resources as alternatives for learning.

Table 21. Comparison in the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters when grouped by Structure

Profile Variable	Affective Filter Variable	F-computed value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Family Structure	Affective Biological Variable	3.83	0.01*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Environmental Variable	1.98	0.12	Accept	Not significant
	Affective Motivational Variable	3.63	0.01*	Reject	Significant
	Affective Social Variable	2.39	0.07	Accept	Not significant

Finally, for the variable of family structure, the analysis indicated a significant difference in the level of affective filters based on family structure. The affective filters of biological and motivational factors showed significant differences. The F-values ranged from 1.98 to 3.83, and the associated p-values were all below the significance level. This means that family structure contributes to the increase or reduction of affective filters of students in their biological and motivational variables. Specifically, when learners are living in extended or nuclear families, the result signifies that this factor influences their personal traits and motivational aspects.

However, no significant differences were found for the affective filter of environmental and social variables. Therefore, it can be concluded that the level of affective filters differs significantly based on family structure, particularly in the biological and motivational domains.

This result is supported by Petren (2015), who explained that family structure determines the level of participation of learners in school. It influences the behavior and thinking of children under such a structure. Specifically, Brown (2016) revealed that the extended family structure adversely affects learners' performance in school due to cited conditions such as no single form of a behavioral model and the adverse effects of multiple parenting.

In a longitudinal study done by Battaglia et al., (2017) they found that children who experienced persistent dependence and meek behavior who were raised in extended families between ages 1.5 and 6 years went on to show more internalizing symptoms, worse overall academic achievement, and poorer physical health later in childhood and preadolescence. While some research suggests nuclear being in isolation may not impact

a student's academic achievement, other research has found a strong correlation between filial ties and academic and social success (Brannlund et al., 2017).

Relationship between the Respondents' Level of Affective Filters and Academic Performance

Table 22. Relationship between the Level of Affective Filters and Academic Performance of the Respondents

Affective Filters	Pearson r – Value	P-value	Interpretation
Biological	0.48	0.00	Significant
Environmental	0.55	0.00	Significant
Motivational	0.46	0.00	Significant
Social	0.38	0.00	Significant

The table provides insights into the relationship between the level of affective filters and the respondents' academic performance.

Starting with the Affective Biological Variable, the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.48. This indicates a moderately positive relationship between the level of affective filters in the biological domain and the respondents' academic performance. The p-value associated with this relationship is 0.00, which indicates that the relationship is statistically significant. This categorically means that personal traits, features, and characteristics of learners significantly influence and affect their academic performance. When their Affective Biological Variable is low, it is more likely that learners will develop academic success.

Moving to the Affective Environmental Variable, the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.55. This indicates a strong positive relationship between the level of affective filters in the environmental domain and academic performance. The p-value of 0.00 suggests that this relationship is statistically significant. This result signifies that environmental aspects and circumstances of learners are contributory factors in their academic success and learning development. In a nutshell, learners' physical environment which includes their homes, communities, internal and external premises, classrooms, and school premises, makes a significant contribution to the increase or reduction of learners' academic achievement.

Next, the Affective Motivational Variable exhibits a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.46. This indicates a positive relationship between the level of affective filters in the motivational domain and academic performance. The p-value of 0.00 indicates that this relationship is statistically significant. The result implies that intrinsic and extrinsic motivation factors exhibited by the learners affect their academic performance.

Lastly, the Affective Social Variable has a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.38. This indicates a moderately positive relationship between the level of affective filters in

the social domain and academic performance. The p-value of 0.00 confirms the statistical significance of this relationship. In sum, when a positive correlation is obtained between affective social variables and academic performance, this shows that social environment and social circumspect of learners are contributory factors to their academic success. These social factors include but are not limited to their family members, peers, friends, classmates, teachers, or other significant higher authorities.

In summary, the table reveals that there is a significant relationship between the level of affective filters and the academic performance of the respondents. The strength of the relationship varies across the affective filter categories, with the Environmental variable showing the strongest relationship ($r = 0.55$), followed by Biological ($r = 0.48$), Motivational ($r = 0.46$), and Social ($r = 0.38$). These findings suggest that the affective factors in these domains play a role in influencing the academic performance of the respondents.

The results of the study confirmed the findings of Lingam (2018), which revealed that one of the critical factors that negatively affect students' academic performance is the affective filters in the form of social environments, such as a lack of guidance provided by teachers and academic supervisors. Also, Muwonge et al. (2021) found that poor social support from school administrators and supervisors from the school, too many students in some schools, poor allocation of teaching load in various schools, and being unjustly shifted from their original schools of posting are forms of affective filters that reduce academic performance.

In the context of educational outcomes in the new normal, Salacup (2021) revealed that students' low level of academic performance in their subjects is attributed to various affective filters such as a lack of filial and scaffolding support and insufficiency of teaching provisions. Moreover, it also cited that learners' emotional and social conditions affected their behavior and performance in the subject. Hence, affective filters manifest backlogs in the instruction processes (Nayir, 2020), such as a lack of classroom ambience and a lack of motivational and social support

Finally, as pointed out by Evans (2021), educators are a key factor in improving a learner's mental health and in reducing their affective filters, with much of a learner's time being spent in school, educators are more aware of mental health disorders will be more prepared to better support and implement strategies into their schools and classrooms to support all students. Hence, there should be mechanisms adapted to mitigate the adverse effects of mental health issues and concerns in relation to affective filters as contributory factors in the learning development and academic performance of learners.

Conclusions

In light of the dynamic educational system in the country, the study has established that learners manifest a moderately favorable level of affective filters and satisfactory academic performance. The differences in affective filters are explained by academic

performance and learners' ethnicity, family structure, parents' highest educational attainment, nature of employment, and monthly net family income.

Generally, the study posits that least favorable or low affective filters yield higher academic performance. This notion is congruent with various educational principles modeling the importance of intrinsic and extrinsic factors in the learning development of students, including the social cognitive theory, the principle of behaviorism, physiological factors such as socio-economic status, and the environmental set-up of learning conditions. Hence, academic performance is also affected by learning walls called affective filters, teachers, administrators, parents, and guidance advocates must consider them in their instructional and psychosocial support.

Recommendations

After having analyzed the results of this study, the following are recommended:

1. Since it was found that affective filters are moderately favorable and negatively influence academic performance, it is vital that schools' division and schools develop and establish a supported and contextualized curriculum that centers on the affective needs of the students such as the integration of mental health education in the curriculum and personality education and development in the Junior High School level. Further, learning objectives and competencies must also be aligned with effective learning standards. Teacher-made instructional Materials may also be innovated considering students' unique needs and conditions.
2. Since the Affective Motivational Variable, Affective Biological Variable, and Affective Environmental Variable have a moderately favorable level of affective filters, factors that affect the motivational status and aspects of students' learning must also be strengthened. In schools' guidance and counseling functions, guidance counselors or any guidance advocates in schools may innovate special programs to enhance the motivational and emotional learning conditions of learners. These may be done through school symposia on understanding oneself, and coping mechanisms to stresses, anxiety, and other emotional conditions. School heads, administrators, and supervisors may integrate such programs and innovations in their School Improvement Plan or Annual Improvement Plan for budgeting and supervisory purposes.
3. Since the Affective Social Variable obtained the favorable mean of the Affective Filter Variable, it is recommended that the school's external community, including barangays, as part of the school's external stakeholders, may implement programs and projects on family relations and parenting. The Youth Sector of the barangay may initiate a particular project focusing on educational support for students who are experiencing cognitive and non-cognitive backlogs in their classes. Furthermore, in coordination with the Local Government Unit or Non-Governmental Organizations and private sectors, the barangay may succinctly

establish livelihood projects and employment opportunities for the unemployed and families below the poverty threshold.

4. Finally, the concept of affective filters as a novelty in education research may also be undertaken in other school subjects through different learning modalities. Future studies may also highlight and introduce new effective filters aside from the identified filters from previous studies.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author hereby declares that this research was conducted with adherence to ethical standards, ensuring the well-being and privacy of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all students before data collection, and their anonymity was maintained throughout the study. The data was analyzed with sensitivity and respect for the diverse backgrounds and experiences of the participants. The findings are presented objectively and without bias, aiming to contribute to a better understanding of the role of affective filters in educational settings. All sources used in this research have been properly cited and acknowledged, and no plagiarism has occurred. This research is intended to be used for the advancement of educational practices and to promote the well-being of students.

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